

Environmental enrichment and winter garden in a turkey barn

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Introduction

In October 2022, the EURCAW Poultry-SFA visited a turkey barn with a winter garden and environmental enrichment. These additions allow for the production of turkeys without mutilations (intact beak and toes), improving their welfare. A winter garden and natural light indoors were added in 2018 to this 1000 m² barn dating from the 1980s. Since 2017, a partnership with a farm animal welfare NGO has helped to develop a better living environment for the turkeys. During our visit, birds were 71 days old and, a slower-growing strain was being tested. Previously, a white fast-growing strain was housed in the same conditions.

The winter garden

The winter garden is an extra space of 325 m² which provides fresh air access to the birds. It runs contiguously along one full length of the barn, with west exposure, and a net that separates turkeys from the outside. The entire ground surface is covered with chopped straw and shavings (same litter in the barn) and there is no access to food or water in this area. The addition of clean litter is done by the producer every two weeks in the winter garden (and two to three times per week inside the barn). The winter garden offers a space totally differentiated from the rest of the barn and stimulating for turkeys who have a choice to move in different types of environments.

Figure 1: View of the winter garden from the outside (©ANSES)

2600 males and 2600 females are housed separately in this barn. The stocking density is around 5.2 birds/m² excluding the winter garden area (stocking density decreases with the winter garden to less than 4 birds/m²). The birds have access to the winter garden 24/24h, from 35 days of age, except during the first nights when they are kept inside. The females are sent to slaughter at 14 or 15 weeks of age whereas the males stay until 19 or 20 weeks of age.

Figure 2: Turkey on a platform in the winter garden (©ANSES)

Environmental enrichment

Several types of environmental enrichment are available in the winter garden and inside the barn. They allow for different types of behaviours such as foraging, pecking, hiding from conspecifics and perching:

- Straw bales (renew when destroyed) (Figures 3 and 4)
- Elevated platforms with and without ramps (and a place to hide underneath) (Figures 5 and 6)
- Plastic jugs and bottles (Figures 7 and 8)
- Strings (Figures 9 and 10)
- Pecking blocks (Figure 11)

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Figure 3: Straw bale in the winter garden (©ANSES)

Figure 4: Straw bale in the winter garden (©ANSES)

Figure 5: Elevated platform in winter garden (©ANSES)

Figure 6: Elevated platform (1 m height) with ramps inside the barn (©ANSES)

Figure 7: Plastic bottle inside the barn (©ANSES)

Figure 8: Plastic jugs inside the barn (©ANSES)

Figure 9: Strings inside the barn (©ANSES)

Figure 10: Strings in the winter garden (©ANSES)

Figure 11: Pecking stone in the winter garden (©ANSES)

Adding environmental enrichment, natural light and the possibility to access a differentiated space with fresh air thanks to a winter garden allows birds to express their natural behaviours, thus improving their welfare. Turkeys with intact beaks and toes are kept successfully in this system, however, close monitoring is needed because feather pecking may still develop in some flocks.